

**PERSPECTIVES ON SKILLS EFFICIENCY OF TRAINERS
AND MANAGEMENT OF TRAINING TOWARDS EFFECTIVE TRAINING**

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Abstract

The purpose of this research was to investigate the characteristics that impact in-service competence trainers to provide effective training in the South African Police Service (SAPS). To find the 500 respondents, this study used a quantitative strategy that relied on a basic random sampling procedure. Respondents, primarily SAPS members from 13 police stations in Gauteng province, South Africa, completed and returned 329 questionnaires in total. The cohort under research was selected using a non-probability sample technique (purposive), which included respondents from various ranks who attended various training development sessions at the Johannesburg Training Centre. The findings indicated that the demand for trainers' recruitment is laden with various obstacles, such as the already existing paucity of

resources at training centres, lack of communication and transparency, The study also found that more than 70% of respondents said their training is linked with theoretical content and has a direct influence on their daily work. This study provides insights on improving trainer skill efficiency and training management, as well as identifying opportunities for further research. This study offers insight on the elements that influence training quality in the SAPS and proposes appropriate measures for improvement.

Keywords: *competence, trainers, effective, training, police.*

Introduction

As lifelong learning becomes more important, concerns concerning the effectiveness and efficiency of trainers, training, and development towards increased performance are becoming more pressing (Andersen, Pitel, Weerasinghe & Papazoglou, 2016; Blumberg, Schlosser, Papazoglou, Creighton & Kaye, 2019; Mofokeng & Grootboom, 2023). Over the past forty years, a wide amount of study has been produced in several distinct disciplines, including innovation studies, sociology, economics, economic history, psychology, and education, concerning skills, knowledge, and innovation (Bäck, Vallès, & Padyab, 2017; Burgess, Propper, Ratto & Tominey, 2017; Karp, Kohlstrom, Rantatalo & Payed, 2020). Public policy makers have also shown a greater interest in it in more recent times (Erismann, Pesantes, Beran, 2021; Gollust, Seymour, Pany, Goss, Meisel & Grande, 2017; Kay, 2017; Scott, Larson, Buckingham, Maton & Crowley, 2019). It is vital to first review the existing research about the in-service competency of trainers before considering the potential influence of trainers on training results. Any organisation's ability to achieve its goals and objectives is greatly influenced by the effectiveness of its trainers (Al-Khaled & Chung, 2021; Andoh, Mensah & Owusu, 2022; Wisshak & Hochholding, 2019). To keep the business functioning towards realizing quality service delivery, employees' competence and productivity will need to be increased through training (Bonnes, Wißhak, Hochholding, 2019). The primary goal is to eradicate performance issues and help employees enhance their knowledge and abilities in accordance with job requirements (Surbhi, 2015; Toner, 2011). Trainees should therefore be able to fully comprehend the job requirements of an organisation where they work after completing the training (Barzegar & Farjad, 2011; EL Hajjar & Alkhanaizi, 2018; Shin, Kim Kim & Kang, 2020).

After being selected, newly hired employees participate in instruction courses to acclimate themselves to the organisation's policies, procedures, and rules (EL Hajjar & Alkhanaizi, 2018;

Mohammed, 2022; Mvuyisi & Mbukanma, 2023). Courses of study are usually organised by organisations to improve employee performance. These training programmes are designed to help employees perform better toward their supervisors, subordinates, and coworkers as well as to prepare them for future employment (Diamantidis & Chatzoglou, 2014; Voegtlin, Boehm & Bruch, 2015). Put another way, having skilled staff members could assist the company get to the top in its sector. Members may be able to learn the proper processes to keep up with the demands of the job by providing training (EL Hajjar & Alkhanaizi, 2018). By offering training, an organisation may demonstrate its commitment to its staff, which in turn encourages them to feel valued, challenged, and more satisfied with their work. It is appropriate for organisations to increase employee potential through required training to maximise production and revenue. Employees will have a greater competitive advantage because of these training initiatives. On the other hand, it's equally critical that training programmes cater to the needs of both teams and individual workers. Furthermore, learners may see tangible benefits in the workplace following the training, such as the ability to impart their newly acquired knowledge and abilities to other staff members (EL Hajjar & Alkhanaizi, 2018). This study dealt with skills efficiency of trainers and management of training towards effective training.

Police stations across the Gauteng province serve many purposes, but the overriding imperative is providing services to the public. across the Gauteng province serve many purposes, but the overriding imperative is providing services to the public. The functions and design of police stations differ around the country depending on where they are located, their level of resources and other circumstances. Once employees have been recruited, they must be trained to acquire the knowledge and skills they require for optimal performance. Ongoing, rapid change in the police environment in South Africa calls for all employees and managers to be continuously trained and developed. Police management faces both external changes, such as globalisation, increased competition, technological advancement, and new legislation, as well as drastic internal change such as new systems, policies, procedures, methods, and techniques. The South African Police Service (SAPS), which offers a variety of human resource training programmes, is the subject of this study's chosen training academy. A wide range of training programmes, including those in detective work, visible policing, customer relationship management, and other management skills, are available at the Johannesburg Training Center.

These programmes are focused on operational and leadership skills. Future training plan modifications and organisational changes may directly arise from assessing the effectiveness of trainers. Furthermore, it does cost money, time, and effort. It is appropriate for an

organisation to evaluate the return on its investment in training. If investing in training is necessary, it is important to consider the return on that investment. The evaluation of the influence that trainers' effectiveness has on an organisation must pay attention to the performance and behaviours of its trainees in order to assess the efficacy of its training initiatives (Kirkpatrick & Kirkpatrick, 2016). This study's primary goal was to investigate, from the trainees' points of view, the variables influencing trainers' efficacy in providing effective instruction at the Johannesburg Training Centre. This goal is broken down into the following specific objectives:

- Identify the effective factors that, from the trainees' perspective, affect trainers' efficiency;
- Investigate the relationship between these factors and training effectiveness;
- Identify the impact of these factors on training effectiveness.

The investigation's findings will assist human resource professionals in enhancing their training initiatives. The input received from the attendees regarding their evaluation of the trainers' effectiveness and the way they subsequently applied the knowledge and dispositions acquired from it aided the HR professionals in pinpointing areas in need of development. Similarly, this study assists the SAPS in ascertaining whether its training initiatives correspond with its organisational goals. The SAPS and other law enforcement organizations may find it easier to verify whether their people are adequately trained to perform their jobs if training evaluation is used. Similarly, the results of this research may aid law enforcement organisations in improving the quality of their training initiatives. Training managers might be able to determine whether the requirements are met by their training programmes. The SAPS management may be able to rectify the shortcomings of their training programme with the aid of the outcomes. This study uses the terms "competence," "knowledge," and "skill" interchangeably to refer to the ability of trainers based on the presentation of practical skills within a particular workplace, with minimal emphasis on teaching or assessing theoretical underpinnings.

Literature Review

Theoretical and Conceptual Background

According to Grootboom and Mofokeng (2023), the SAPS is the main law enforcement organisation and plays a significant part in enhancing public safety. Organisational and operational priorities make up the SAPS's strategies. With a focus on creating safer communities, the National Development Plan (NDP) Vision 2030 is a clear inspiration for the SAPS's 2020–2022 Strategic Plan. The police are emphasised in the NDP Vision 2030 as a

highly skilled force that is manned by professionals with adequate resources, who value their work, serve the community, defend the peaceful against violence, and uphold the rights of all people to equality and justice (South Africa, 2011). Through strategic outcome-oriented goals, such as an efficient, effective, and developing public service, this futuristic strategy focuses on professionalizing the police. It is recommended that SAPS management use training to enhance the competencies of police officers to boost employee enthusiasm and performance. The significance of training and skill development is also emphasised in the NDP Vision 2030 (South Africa, 2011).

The Republic of South Africa, 1996 (henceforth referred to as the Constitution) stipulates in Section 206 (1) that the cabinet minister in charge of policing must decide on the national policing policy after conferring with the provincial governments and considering the priorities and needs for policing as established by the provincial executives. "Citizens should be consulted about the level and quality of the public services they receive and, wherever possible, should be given a choice as to the services being offered," according to the White Paper on Transforming Public Service Delivery (Batho Pele Principles), which aligns with the Constitution's mandate (South Africa, 1997, p.15). It goes on to say that consultation can support the development of a more cooperative and participatory relationship between the people who offer public services and those who use them. Communities should be consulted to ascertain their policing requirements and priorities, in accordance with the Constitution, laws, and the Batho Pele Principles. Published standards for service quality ought to be implemented at the federal, state, and local levels. These criteria ought to be quantifiable, explicit, and meaningful to each user. It should be possible for users to determine whether the promised services were provided (South Africa, 1997).

When it comes to service delivery in the SAPS, professionalism is mandated by the Constitution, the SAPS Act (No. 68 of 1995), the NDP, 2011, the White Paper on Safety and Security, and other legal documents. According to Section 206 (1) of the Constitution, the cabinet minister in charge of law enforcement is required to confer with provincial governments and consider the priorities and needs for law enforcement as established by the provincial executives before deciding on the national policing strategy. Although there are policies, guidelines and laws that regulate SAPS conduct it has been documented that the conduct of SAPS members is contrary to what the Constitution and the White Paper prescribes. In a stable democratic dispensation, the conduct of police officials is viewed as the symbol of a democratic government, which is contrary to what is happening at the ground (Govender & Pillay, 2022).

Burger (2016) suggests that for SAPS to gain confidence and legitimacy, they must remove any grain of fear and resentment that still persist post-apartheid. This change can be attained through their willingness to change their attitude, behaviour, systems, and approach when dealing with citizens. For effective policing to take place, the alienation between the police and the public must change, where the perception of “us versus them” is replaced a common effort (Burger, 2016). In addition, the most effective way of ensuring that Batho Pele principle is upheld is for all stakeholders involved to acknowledge that since the Constitution is the ultimate law of the land, all laws, policies, and plans pertaining to the provision of public services must be compliant with it. In addition, it serves as a blueprint for the transformation of the public service to deliver services to the public effectively (Modise, Taylor & Raga, 2020). The improved delivery of government services is covered in Chapters 3 and 10 of the Constitution, which stipulate that public administration must uphold several democratic values and principles, such as:

- The promotion and maintenance of a high standard of professional ethics;
- the efficient, economical, and effective use of resources;
- the development-oriented nature of public administration; the impartiality, fairness, equity, and lack of bias in the provision of services;
- the consideration of people's needs and the encouragement of public participation in policymaking; public administration's accountability;
- the promotion of transparency through the provision of timely, accurate, and accessible information to the public;
- the cultivation of good human resource management and career-development practices to maximize human potential; and
- the public administration's employment and personnel management practices based on ability, objectivity, fairness and the need to redress the imbalances of the past to achieve broad representation.

Trainer Competency

According to Glarum, Joseph, McKenny and Fritzsche (2020) and Sitzmann, Brown, Casper and Zimmerman (2008), the trainer may be crucial to the success of formal training. Noe (2010, 2005) states that trainers can usually work in a variety of roles, including needs analysis, technical trainer, and instructional designer. If those providing the training lack pedagogical competence, it will not be effective. However, the training literature does not pay enough

attention to how trainers' pedagogical competencies affect employees' acquisition of information and skills throughout training (Andoh et al., 2022). The trainer's job is to guide learners through the process of changing their behaviour (Maimunah, 2001). Bohlander and Snell (2004) assert that a training programme's performance is greatly influenced by the trainers' interpersonal qualities and instructional abilities. To increase the success of the training programme, trainers also set performance standards for trainees during training and inspire and motivate them to learn (Forsyth, Jolliffe & Stevens, 1995). (Power, 1992). Trainers' competencies are divided into two categories by Mamaqi, Miguel, and Olave (2011): fundamental (pedagogical) and (skills, abilities, aptitude/attitude, and qualities). Nonetheless, Ghosh, Satyawadi, Joshi, Ranjan, and Singh (2012) tried to identify the factors that predict training success, paying particular attention to the traits of trainers. Only the trainer's connection with the trainees and degree of comfort with the subject matter were found to be significant predictors of trainee satisfaction out of the seven variables that were assessed. According to an article published by Chukwu (2016), trainees' recognition of seven key teacher traits in post-training evaluations indicates that the training was successful. One facilitator's temperament, two real-life examples, three group projects, four interactions, five participant engagement, six stories/illustrations, and seven demonstrations are the traits. These trainers' qualities work in concert with the surrounding circumstances to cause trainee traits that result in altered behaviour and increased performance.

Methodology

Measurement of Constructs

Utilizing a quantitative research methodology, this study serves as a measure to identify the components among all independent variables that contribute to training efficacy and supports previous findings. By employing a survey method, a quantitative approach was used. By using this quantitative approach, the respondents were given questionnaires to complete to collect primary data. This approach was selected by the researchers since it is the most appropriate one for this study and allows them to get precise data from participants. A research project's study design is a framework that outlines the steps required to gather the data needed to formulate or address issues (Babbie & Mouton, 2018). To find out how effective the trainers had been with the responders; the researchers conducted a descriptive study. A descriptive study is conducted, according to Babbie and Mouton (2018), to identify and be able to characterize the variables of interest in each situation; for instance, to characterize the

characteristics of respondents from each police station with respect to age, education level, position grade, and preferred training types. Descriptive research is also conducted to comprehend the traits of organisations that adhere to standard procedures.

For instance, the SAPS training centre has established benchmarks for members to meet in terms of the amount of training sessions they attend annually. Any research project needs to take ethical considerations into consideration, but this is especially true when working with human subjects. Therefore, to perform any research, ethical clearance and approval are required. The SAPS had to first authorize the request to conduct research before the university could offer ethical clearance for this study. This was subsequently modified to full ethical clearance after the SAPS approved the research request. In compliance with the National Instruction of 2006, authorisation was sought and approved by the Gauteng Provincial Office in consultation with the pre-selected police stations. To give the lead researcher, contact information and permit the researcher to proceed with the research, the Gauteng Provincial Office got in touch with the chosen police stations. The police officials who operate in the study region and are aware of the training activities are the sample unit. They also know how much this concept applies to their local policing areas and, more importantly, how it influences crime prevention to achieve organisational goals.

Unit of Analysis

There were only permanent employees among the respondents that took part in this study. Only the instruction they received from the SAPS top management whether from the training unit or from any other programme offered by the university was covered.

Data Collection Method

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to achieve organisational goals. A straightforward random sample technique was used to select 500 respondents for a survey that was distributed to respondents from 13 police stations within the Johannesburg policing region. 329 surveys, mostly from SAPS members in the province of Gauteng, were completed and returned by respondents. The cohort under research, or the respondents from various ranks who attended various training courses at the Johannesburg Training Centre, was chosen using a non-probability sample technique (purposive) to get their opinions on skills efficiency of trainers and management of training towards effective training of trainees.

Method of Data Analysis

To make inferences, the gathered data were analysed using chi-square goodness of fit testing and descriptive analysis. Excel was used to record the responses, which were then transferred to the Statistical Programme for Social Sciences (SPSS) for additional processing and coding. If there were any correlations or links between the demographic characteristics and the respondents' attitudes, they were examined using a chi-square test of independence (X^2). More broadly, it examines if there are differences between the distributions of category variables. For sets of data that are to be associated, it is crucial to identify the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis before applying this test (Fourie & Chimusoro, 2018).

Analysis

The sample included African, White and Coloured respondents, all employed in terms of the Police Act. The ranks comprised of: Constables: 38 percent ($n=126$; 38.4%); Sergeants: 29 percent ($n=95$; 28.9%); Warrant Officers: 13 percent ($n=41$; 12.5%). The commissioned officers (i.e. Captains, Lieutenant Colonels, Colonels and Brigadiers), comprised of 20 percent ($n=67$; 20.4%) combined. Males constituted of 70 percent ($n=172$; 70.4%) responses, with female respondents constituting the least number of respondents at 30 percent ($n=157$; 29.6%). Not only were females minimally represented, but they were also likely to be found in the lowest ranks. This might be linked to the history of the policing profession or other factors. The p -value is $0.043 < 0.05$, which suggests a link between gender and rank. Furthermore, global trends indicate that fewer women than men are considering careers in law enforcement (Hau-Nung & Ho, 2013; Helfgott, Gunnison, Murtagh & Navejar, 2018; Rabe-Hemp, 2009). Most of the subordinates were aged 20–30 ($n=293$; 90.9%), followed by ages 31–40 ($n=11$; 3.3%). Few respondents were over 41 years old ($n=19$; 5.8%). All subordinates were equally

represented across, with all age groups decreasing as the responsibility of policing decreases. The p -value is $0.040 < 0.05$, which indicates a significant link between age and experience or service. According to the respondents' employment categories, Visible Policing (n=149; 45.29%) and Detective Training Academy (n=154; 46.8%) accounted for the bulk of the respondents. Finally, n=26 (7.9%) made up the support workforce.

Results

Statement 1: Skills efficiency of trainers

Perceptions on whether the trainer explains the outcomes of the course

Table 1 indicates that 78% of the respondents, by years of service, agreed that the trainer explains the outcomes of the course and 10% disagreed. The data shows significant differences with $P = 0.044$.

Table 1: Respondents' perceptions on whether the trainer explains the outcomes of the course by years of service

Year of service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 – 3	10(20.41)	27(55.10)	7(14.29)	4(8.16)	1(2.04)	49(100.00)
4 – 6	3(7.50)	22(55.00)	8(20.00)	7(17.50)	0(0.00)	40(100.00)
7 -9	9(14.06)	9(14.06)	44(68.75)	8(12.50)	1(1.56)	64(100.00)
10 -12	2(7.69)	13(50.00)	5(19.23)	4(15.38)	2(7.69)	26(100.00)
13	24(16.11)	101(67.79)	13(8.72)	10(6.71)	1(0.67)	149(100.00)
Total	48(14.63)	207(63.11)	41(12.50)	27(8.23)	5(1.52)	328(100.00)

Chi-square = 26.7593 P = 0.044

In terms of the different categories of respondents, Table 2 shows that commanders and the 'other' groups do not share the understanding of the rest of the groups. While some respondents did not agree that trainers explain the outcomes of courses, it will be difficult to solve this problem without physical motoring of trainers. In terms of courses attended, there were no significant differences in responses to this question and the views expressed were very positive.

Table 2: Respondents’ perceptions on whether the trainers explain the outcomes of the course by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely		
Total	Chiz	PV					
	agree				disagree		
Commander	5	23	11	1	0	40	10.980
	10.42	11.06	26.83	3.85	0.00	12.20	
Supervisor	6	34	6	3	0	49	1.667
	12.50	16.35	14.63	11.54	0.00	14.94	
Trainee	31	131	21	18	5	206	5.844
	64.58	62.98	51.22	69.23	100.00	62.80	
Trainer	3	20	1	3	0	27	3.423
	6.25	9.62	2.44	11.54	0.00	8.23	
Others	4	27	9	6	2	48	7.796
	8.33	12.98	21.95	23.08	40.00	14.63	
Total	49	235	48	31	7	370	

Courses	Definitely	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely	Total	Chiz
PV	agree				disagree		
attended							
Detectives	14	64	12	9	0	99	2.568
	29.79	32.16	33.33	34.62	0.00	31.63	
Mentor	6	34	6	3	0	31	2.
	12.77	16.35	14.63	11.54	0.00	9.90	
Train the	10	27	4	3	0	31	2.431
trainer	21.28	13	11.11	11.54	0.00	9.90	
Junior	9	22	4	4	0	39	3.423

management	19.15	11.06	11.11	15.38	0.00	12.46	
National	4	23	3	1	1	45	2.534
1.000							
certificate	8.51	11	8.33	3.85	20.00	14.38	
Senior	5	10	2	2	0	19	2.561
1.000							
management	10.64	5.03	5.56	7.69	0.00	6.07	
CSC	11	47	9	9	1	77	1.606
1.000							
Others	4	27	9	6	2	48	7.796
0.497							
	23.40	23.62	25.00	34.62	20.00	24.60	
Total	69	288	50	37	5	449	

Statement 2: Perceptions on whether trainers relate theoretical content to practical examples

Table 3 reveals that 73% of the respondents agreed and 8% disagreed that trainers relate theoretical content to practical examples. This suggests that the training centre is heading in the right direction in terms of its mandate of empowering police officials. However, some station commanders were of the view that the traditional culture of instruction and command was impeding progress.

Table 3: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers relate theoretical content to practical examples by years of service

Year of service	Definitel agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 – 3	10(20.41)	28(57.14)	9(18.37)	1(2.04)	1(2.04)	49(100.00)
4 – 6	3(7.50)	23(57.50)	8(20.00)	6(15.00)	0(0.00)	40(100.00)
7 -9	10(15.63)	41(64.06)	10(15.63)	2(3.13)	1(1.56)	64(100.00)
10 -12	3(11.54)	11(42.31)	7(26.92)	3(11.54)	2(7.69)	26(100.00)
13	25(17.45)	85(57.05)	29(19.46)	6(4.03)	3(2.01)	3(100.00)
Total	52(15.85)	188(57.32)	63(19.21)	18(5.49)	7(2.13)	328(100.00)

Chi-square = 21.0994 P = 0.175

Regarding the different categories of respondents, Table 3 shows that the views of respondents in the ‘others’ category differed significantly from those of commanders, supervisors, trainees, and trainers. The results suggest that trainers should be exposed to field work at police stations. For example, they could spend a year providing training and three months at a station to update their knowledge in the field. Trainers who opted for this job as they do not want to perform certain duties at stations are a challenge. An effective trainer is a researcher by nature. In terms of courses attended, the responses did not significantly differ from one another.

Table 4: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers relate theoretical content to practical examples by category and courses attended

Category PV	Definitel agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz
Commander 1.000	8	18	12	2	0	40	5.491
	15.38	9.52	19.05	11.76	0.00	12.20	
Supervisor 1.000	7	31	9	2	0	49	1.793
	13.46	16.40	14.29	11.76	0.00	14.94	
Trainee 1.000	32	123	34	11	6	206	4.159
	61.54	65.08	53.97	64.71	85.71	62.80	
Trainer 1.000	4	15	7	1	0	27	1.485
	7.69	7.94	11.11	5.884	0.00	8.23	
Others 0.001	1	23	15	6	3	48	22.162
	1.92	12.17	23.81	35.29	42.86	14.63	
Total	52	210	77	22	9	370	

Courses PV attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz
Detectives 1.000	16	63	14	5	1	99	3.176
	31.37	34.81	24.56	29.41	14.29	31.63	
Mentor 1.000	7	24	8	2	0	41	1.147
	13.73	13.26	14.04	11.76	0.00	13.10	
Train the 1.000 trainer	4	20	6	1	0	31	1.611
	7.84	11.05	10.53	5.88	0.00	9.90	
Junior 1.000 management	10	17	9	3	0	39	5.946
	19.15	9.39	15.79	17.65	0.00	12.46	
National 1.000	8	26	7	3	1	45	0.422

certificate	15.69	14.36	12.28	17.65	14.29	14.38	
Senior	6	9	2	2	0	19	5.358
1.000							
management	11.76	4.97	3.51	11.76	0.00	4.07	
CSC	15	42	12	6	2	77	2.321
1.000							
Others	29.41	23.20	21.05	35.29	28.57	24.60	
1.000	13	57	21	4	3	98	2.530
Total	25.41	31.49	36.84	23.53	42.86	31.31	
	79	258	79	26	7	449	

Statement 3: Perceptions on whether trainers give clear answers to questions in class

Overall, 71% of the respondents agreed and 11% disagreed that trainers give clear answers to questions in class. The responses differed significantly with a P-value of 0.032. Learning is a two-way process. While, in the past, trainers could enter the lecture room unprepared and there was no evaluation at the end of the lesson, modern-day police training measures up to that provided by other training institutions.

Table 5: Respondents' perceptions on whether trainers give clear answers to questions in class by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 – 3	7(14.29)	27(55.10)	7(14.29)	7(14.29)	1(2.04)	49(100.00)
4 – 6	6(15.00)	13(32.50)	14(35.00)	7(17.50)	0(0.00)	40(100.00)
7 – 9	9(14.06)	44(68.75)	9(14.06)	1(1.56)	1(1.56)	64(100.00)
10 – 12	2(7.69)	12(46.15)	7(26.92)	4(15.38)	1(3.85)	26(100.00)
13	19(12.75)	93(62.42)	24(16.11)	11(7.38)	2(1.34)	149(100.00)
Total	43(13.11)	189(57.62)	61(18.60)	30(9.15)	5(1.52)	328(100.00)

Chi-square = 28.0023 P = 0.032

Table 6 shows that the views of respondents in the 'others' category differed significantly to those of the rest of the groups with a P-value of 0.092 as well as in respect of courses attended

at 0.602. Most of the respondents confirmed that trainers provide clear answers to questions during class. The largest group of respondents attended the detective course, and their responses did not differ significantly.

Table 6: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers give clear answers to questions in class by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	6	22	10	2	0	40	2.650	1.000
	13.95	11.58	16.39	6.90	0.00	12.20		
Supervisor	6	32	7	3	1	49	1.733	1.000
	13.95	16.84	11.48	10.34	20.00	14.94		
Trainee	25	119	38	20	4	206	1.514	1.000
	58.14	62.63	62.30	68.97	80.00	62.80		
Trainer	5	16	4	2	0	27	1.409	1.000
	11.63	8.42	6.56	6.90	0.00	8.23		
Others	1	27	10	8	2	48	11.863	0.092
	2.33	14.21	16.39	27.59	40.00	14.63		
Total	43	216	69	35	7	370		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	12	58	19	10	0	99	2.920	1.000
	28.58	31.69	35.19	34.48	0.00	31.63		
Mentor	4	25	8	4	0	41	1.428	1.000
	9.52	13.66	14.81	13.79	0.00	13.10		
Train the trainer	4	21	4	2	0	31	1.734	1.000
	9.52	11.48	7.41	6.90	0.00	9.90		
Junior Management	6	23	6	4	0	39	0.979	1.000
	14.29	12.57	11.11	13.79	0.00	12.46		
National Certificate	8	25	5	7	0	45	5.053	1.000
	19.05	13.66	9.26	24.14	0.00	14.38		
Senior Management	4	12	2	1	0	19	2.158	1.000
	8.52	6.56	3.70	3.45	0.00	6.07		
CSC	14	41	12	9	1	77	3.072	1.000

	33.33	22.40	22.21	31.03	20.00	24.60		
Other	10	62	13	9	4	98	8.488	0.602
	23.81	33.88	24.07	31.03	80.00	31.31		
Total	62	267	69	46	5	449		

Statement 4: Perceptions on trainers’ lack of theoretical knowledge of subjects

In terms of years of service, Table 7 indicates that most of the respondents disagreed with the statement that trainers lack theoretical knowledge of the subjects they present. However, the results show that the responses differed significantly across groups with a P-value of 0.093.

Table 7: Respondents’ perceptions on trainers’ lack of theoretical knowledge of subjects by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 - 3	5(10.20)	10(20.41)	14(28.57)	12(24.49)	8(16.33)	49(100.00)
4 - 6	2(5.00)	12(30.00)	12(30.00)	10(25.00)	4(10.00)	40(100.00)
7 - 9	4(6.25)	23(35.94)	18(28.13)	15(23.44)	4(6.25)	64(100.00)
10 - 12	2(7.69)	14(53.85)	3(11.54)	4(15.38)	3(11.54)	26(100.00)
13	9(6.04)	32(21.48)	39(28.17)	55(36.91)	14(9.40)	149(100.00)
Total	22(6.71)	91(27.74)	86(26.22)	96(29.27)	33(10.06)	328(100.00)

Chi-square = 23.8579 P = 0.093

The responses of trainees, trainers and the ‘others’ group differed significantly from the remaining groups on the question of whether trainers lack theoretical knowledge on their subjects. Trainees’ opinions of trainers are crucial as they listen to them daily. There was some dissatisfaction regarding this issue. In terms of courses attended, significant differences emerged. Respondents that attended mentorship; train the trainer, junior management and national certificate courses had different opinions. Most of the respondents disagreed with the

statement, suggesting that trainers need to attend refresher courses to enhance their knowledge on their subject matter.

Table 8: Respondents’ perceptions on trainers’ lack of theoretical knowledge of subjects by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	3	7	10	17	3	40	4.943	1.000
	13.04	7.69	11.63	17.89	9.09	12.20		
Supervisor	2	11	14	18	4	49	2.817	1.000
	8.70	12.09	16.28	18.95	12.12	14.94		
Trainee	16	64	58	51	17	206	8.631	0.355
	69.57	90.33	67.44	53.68	51.52	62.80		
Trainer	2	7	3	8	7	27	9.968	0.205
	8.70	7.69	3.49	8.42	21.21	8.23		
Others	2	14	18	8	6	48	6.687	0.767
	8.70	15.38	20.93	8.42	18.18	14.63		
Total	25	103	103	102	37	370		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	10	27	26	28	8	99	2.220	1.000
	43.48	30.68	33.33	30.11	25.81	31.63		
Mentor	3	9	5	21	3	41	11.367	0.182
	13.04	10.23	6.41	22.58	9.68	13.10		
Train the trainer	1	5	4	15	6	31	11.689	0.159
	4.35	5.68	5.13	16.13	19.35	9.96		
Junior Management	4	7	7	18	3	39	7.293	0.970
	17.39	7.95	8.97	19.35	9.68	12.46		
National Certificate	0	11	8	17	9	45	11.749	0.155
	0.00	12.50	10.26	18.28	29.03	14.38		
Senior Management	1	6	2	7	3	19	2.941	1.000
	4.35	6.82	2.56	7.53	9.68	6.07		
CSC	6	23	22	21	5	77	2.090	1.000
	26.09	26.14	28.21	22.58	16.13	24.00		
Other	6	25	23	34	10	98	1.961	1.000
	26.09	28.41	29.49	36.56	32.26	31.31		

Total	31	113	97	161	47	449
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Statement 5: Perceptions on whether trainers should continue to present the same subjects

In terms of years of service, Table 9 shows that 66% of the respondents across all categories agreed that trainers should continue presenting the same subjects. The perception was that during apartheid, members joined training centres without going through interviews. Training was not regarded as a priority and a shortage of trainers left management with no option but to accept whoever decided to join. However, the respondents differed significantly in their responses to the question, which indicates that this view might be overturned were this research to be repeated.

Table 9: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers should continue to present the same subjects by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 - 3	6(12.24)	22(44.90)	15(30.61)	5(10.20)	1(2.04)	49(100.00)
4 - 6	9(22.50)	14(35.00)	7(17.50)	9(22.50)	1(2.50)	40(100.00)
7 - 9	7(10.94)	37(57.81)	15(23.44)	3(4.69)	2(3.13)	64(100.00)
10 - 12	4(15.38)	10(38.46)	6(23.08)	5(19.23)	1(3.85)	26(100.00)
13	19(12.75)	89(59.73)	28(18.79)	8(5.37)	5(3.36)	149(100.00)
Total	45(13.72)	172(52.44)	71(21.65)	30(9.15)	10(3.05)	328(100.00)

Chi-square = 26.1108 P = 0.052

In terms of categories of respondents, there was a slight difference between the ‘others’ group and the rest of the groups on this question with a P-value of 0.052. In terms of courses attended, respondents that attended the senior management certificate course differed significantly with

the rest on how they responded to the question at a P-value of 0.615. The situation that triggered this question was that trainers are presenting different subjects, which makes it difficult to master them.

Table 10: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers should continue to present the same subjects by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	6	19	13	2	0	40	4.920	1.000
	13.33	10.98	18.31	6.90	0.00	12.20		
Supervisor	5	27	11	4	2	49	0.828	1.000
	11.11	15.61	15.49	13.79	20.00	14.94		
Trainee	26	111	43	19	7	206	1.089	1.000
	57.78	64.16	60.56	65.52	70.00	62.80		
Trainer	5	15	3	3	1	27	2.259	1.000
	11.11	8.67	4.23	10.34	10.00	8.23		
Others	3	23	11	7	4	48	9.824	0.217
	6.67	13.29	15.49	24.14	40.00	14.63		
Total	45	195	81	35	14	370		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	11	51	21	13	3	99	3.266	1.000
	55.00	31.10	31.34	44.83	33.33	31.63		
Mentor	6	23	7	4	1	41	0.592	1.000
	13.64	14.02	10.45	13.79	11.11	13.10		
Train the trainer	4	19	5	3	0	31	1.995	1.000
	9.09	11.59	7.46	10.34	0.00	9.90		
Junior Management	5	20	6	7	1	39	4.454	1.000
	11.36	12.20	8.96	24.14	11.11	12.46		
National Certificate	7	20	11	7	0	45	4.701	1.000
	15.91	12.20	16.42	24.14	0.00	14.38		
Senior Management	3	12	0	4	0	19	8.435	0.615
	6.82	7.32	0.00	13.79	0.00	6.07		
CSC	12	41	17	4	3	77	2.401	1.000
	27.27	25.00	25.37	13.79	33.33	24.60		
Other	9	55	22	9	3	98	8.488	0.602

	20.45	33.54	32.84	31.03	33.33	31.31
Total	57	241	89	51	11	449

6: Perceptions on whether trainers are appointed after thorough recruitment

In terms of years of service, table 11 shows that the respondents differed significantly with a P-value of 0.024. Most of the respondents who participated in this study had 13+ years of service and 43% were uncertain on this issue. This suggests that the recruitment of trainers is not as transparent as one would have expected. Management needs to review the current policy to address this situation.

Table 11: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers are appointed after thorough recruitment by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 - 3	6(12.24)	21(42.86)	18(36.73)	3(6.12)	1(2.04)	49(100.00)
4 - 6	7(17.50)	13(32.50)	11(27.50)	8(20.00)	1(2.50)	40(100.00)
7 - 9	3(4.69)	38(59.38)	18(28.13)	3(4.69)	2(3.13)	64(100.00)
10 - 12	0(0.00)	14(53.85)	8(30.77)	3(11.54)	1(3.85)	26(100.00)
13	11(7.38)	54(36.24)	64(42.95)	12(8.05)	8(5.37)	149(100.00)
Total	27(8.23)	140(42.68)	119(36.28)	13(3.96)	13(3.96)	328(100.00)

Chi-square = 28.9507 P = 0.024

Tables 12 shows that, in terms of categories of respondents, the P-values reflect different opinions, with commanders, trainers and those in the ‘others’ category differing on whether trainers are appointed after thorough recruitment. The perception is that recruitment requirements are compromised in many cases due to already existing shortages at the training centre. Some trainers have never worked at a police station as they were taken in after

completing their training at the college. In terms of courses attended, the responses did not significantly differ from one another.

Table 12: Respondents’ perceptions on whether trainers are appointed after thorough recruitment by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	2	12	23	2	1	40	8.952	0.312
	7.14	8.57	19.33	7.14	7.69	12.20		0.312
Supervisor	5	23	16	5	0	49	3.112	1.000
	17.86	16.43	13.45	17.86	0.00	14.94		
Trainee	16	95	71	15	8	206	3.668	1.000
	57.14	67.86	59.66	53.57	69.23	62.80		
Trainer	4	8	7	5	3	27	10.629	0.155
	14.29	5.71	5.88	17.86	23.08	8.23		
Others	3	15	19	8	3	48	7.331	0.597
	10.71	10.71	15.97	28.57	23.08	14.63		
Total	30	153	136	35	16	370		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	7	42	37	9	4	99	0.810	1.000
	25.00	31.11	33.64	32.14	33.33	31.63		
Mentor	3	17	18	2	1	41	2.312	1.000
	10.71	12.59	16.36	7.14	8.33	13.10		
Train the trainer	4	14	7	4	2	31	3.398	1.000
	14.29	10.37	6.36	14.29	16.67	9.90		
Junior Management	2	16	13	7	1	3	5.037	1.000
	7.14	11.85	11.82	25.00	8.33	12.46		
National Certificate	5	16	15	7	2	45	2.642	1.000
	17.86	11.85	13.64	25.00	16.67	14.38		
Senior Management	2	9	5	3	0	19	2.121	1.000
	7.14	6.67	4.55	10.71	0.00	6.09		
CSC	7	38	21	8	3	77	2.958	1.000
	25.00	28.15	19.09	28.57	25.00	24.60		
Other	6	39	40	9	4	98	2.77	1.000

	21.	28.89	36.36	32.14	33.33	31.31
Total	36	191	156	49	17	449

Management of training in the Centre

Variety of courses offered at the Centre

Most of the respondents who completed the questionnaire attended a detective course or CSC at the training centre. The listed courses offered are: Case Administration, Shooting Practice, Mentoring, Victim Empowerment, Junior Management (Basic Management Learning Programme) Senior Management (Officers Course) National Certificate and Train the Trainer.

Statement 7: Perceptions on regular of monitoring of training

The researchers included this question to check if training management takes place only at the training centre or also when members are at their stations. Members are sometimes given a portfolio of evidence to complete at their workplace. This raised questions on who is responsible to ensure that they submit their completed work. This should be the responsibly of station commanders and branch commanders. In terms of years of service, Table 13 shows that the respondents differed significantly in their responses to this question with a P-value of 0.092, which indicates that, while the majority were satisfied, a few were not.

Table 13: Respondents’ perceptions on regular monitoring of training by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 - 3	3(6.12)	25(51.02)	12(24.49)	6(12.24)	3(6.12)	49(100.00)
4 - 6	5(12.50)	20(50.00)	6(15.00)	9(22.50)	0(0.00)	40(100.00)
7 - 9	5(7.81)	35(54.69)	18(28.13)	6(9.38)	0(0.00)	64(100.00)
10 - 12	3(11.54)	11(42.31)	6(23.08)	4(15.38)	2(7.69)	26(100.00)
13	12(8.72)	65(43.62)	51(24.23)	19(12.75)	1(0.67)	149(100.00)

Total	29(8.84)	156(47.56)	93(28.35)	44(13.41)	6(1.83)	328(100.00)
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Chi-square = 23.8768 P = 0.092

In terms of categories of respondents, Table 14 indicates that in terms of categories of respondents, the P-values reflect different opinions, with commanders, trainers, and those in the ‘others’ group feeling that there is poor monitoring of training. However, in terms of courses attended, the responses did not differ significantly. These results were very pertinent in informing the study’s recommendations.

Table 14: Respondents’ perceptions on regular monitoring of training by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	5 17.24	14 8.97	19 20.21	2 4.65	0 0.00	40 12.20	10.963	0.135
Supervisor	7 24.14	23 14.74	13 13.83	6 13.95	0 0.00	49 14.94	3.113	1.000
Trainee	13 44.83	102 65.38	56 59.57	30 69.77	5 83.33	206 62.80	0.851	0.720
Trainer	3 10.34	15 9.62	5 5.32	4 9.30	0 0.00	27 8.23	2.226	1.000
Others	2 6.90	19 12.18	17 18.09	7 16.28	3 50.00	48 14.63	9.139	0.289
Total	30	173	110	49	8	370		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	11 40.74	42 27.63	27 31.76	16 37.21	3 50.00	99 31.63	3.716	1.000
Mentor	5 18.52	20 13.16	12 14.12	4 9.30	0 0.00	41 13.10	2.224	1.000
Train the trainer	3 11.11	16 10.53	6 7.06	6 13.95	0 0.00	31 9.90	2.331	1.000

Junior Management	7	20	7	5	0	39	6.829	1.000
National Certificate	25.93	13.16	8.24	11.63	0.00	12.46		
Senior Management	4	25	8	8	0	45	3.868	1.000
CSC	14.81	16.45	9.41	18.60	0.00	14.38		
Other	4	6	6	3	0	19	5.418	1.000
	14.81	3.95	7.06	6.98	0.00	6.07		
	9	36	18	13	1	77	2.655	1.000
	33.33	23.68	21.18	30.23	16.67	24.60		
	6	48	32	9	3	98	5.758	1.000
	22.22	31.58	37.65	20.93	50.00	31.31		
Total	49	213	116	64	7	449		

Statement 8: Perceptions on feedback

Table 15 shows dissatisfaction with feedback across the respondents by years of service. They differed significantly in their responses to this question with a P-value of 0.52. This suggests that station commanders are not given feedback on members’ course results. It could result in a situation where, for example, a member that is not yet competent is issued with a firearm. Should they shoot a community member SAPS will be liable for civil claim. This question assisted in revealing aspects of training that need to be addressed to improve service delivery to the community.

Table 15: Respondents’ perceptions on whether feedback is given to station commanders and branch commanders by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 - 3	3(6.12)	25(51.02)	11(22.45)	8(16.33)	2(4.08)	49(100.00)
4 - 6	6(15.00)	13(32.50)	13(32.50)	6(15.00)	2(5.00)	40(100.00)
7 - 9	6(9.38)	31(48.44)	22(34.38)	4(6.25)	1(1.56)	64(100.00)
10 - 12	3(11.54)	8(23.08)	6(23.08)	5(19.23)	3(11.54)	26(100.00)
13	14(9.46)	49(33.11)	56(37.84)	24(16.22)	5(3.38)	148(100.00)

Total	32(9.79)	126(38.53)	108(38.53)	47(14.37)	13(3.98)	327(100.00)
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Chi-square = 31.2851 P = 0.052

Regarding occupational categories, Table 16 reveals significant differences in the responses. This suggests that the training centre needs to improve feedback to stations. The question of feedback goes together with monitoring; if there is no monitoring, there will be limited feedback. The commanders and others were not satisfied with the way feedback is given. In terms of courses attended, the respondents who attended mentorship; train the trainer, junior management and senior management certificate courses differed significantly in their responses. This suggests that there are challenges in terms of feedback and communication needs to improve.

Table 16: Respondents’ perceptions on whether feedback is given to station commanders and branch commanders by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	6	9	20	4	1	40	9.298	0.489
	18.75	7.09	18.52	8.70	7.69	12.23		
Supervisor	6	16	19	6	1	48	2.371	1.000
	18.75	12.60	17.59	13.04	7.69	14.48		
Trainee	19	88	60	29	9	206	5.708	1.000
	59.38	69.29	55.56	63.04	69.23	63.00		
Trainer	1	12	8	4	2	27	2.427	1.000
	3.13	9.45	7.41	8.70	15.38	8.26		
Others	4	8	22	12	2	48	14.992	0.052
	12.50	6.30	20.37	26.09	15.38	14.68		
Total	35	133	129	55	15	369		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	10	37	31	13	6	98	3.732	1.000
	31.25	30.08	31.63	28.89	46.15	31.41		
Mentor	5	16	14	5	0	41	9.026	0.804
	15.63	13.01	14.29	11.11	0.00	13.14		
Train the trainer	0	21	6	2	2	31	14.183	0.116
	0.00	17.07	6.12	4.44	15.38	9.94		

Junior	5	12	14	8	0	39	4.564	1.000
Management	15.63	9.76	14.29	17.78	0.00	12.50		
National	5	20	11	8	0	45	9.721	0.668
Certificate	15.63	16.26	11.22	17.78	0.00	14.42		
Senior	1	6	8	4	0	19	3.069	1.000
Management	3.13	4.88	8.16	8.89	0.00	6.09		
CSC	13	25	23	12	4	77	6.391	1.000
	40.63	20.33	23.47	26.67	30.77	24.68		
Other	10	35	33	14	5	97	1.485	1.000
	31.25	28.46	33.67	31.11	38.46	31.09		
Total	49	172	140	66	17	447		

Statement 9: Station Commanders and Branch Commanders’ satisfaction with training

Table 17 shows that, overall, in terms of years of service, 53% of the respondents agreed that station commanders and branch commanders are satisfied with the training provided. However, at the same time, an appreciable number of respondents felt that this was not the case. Police members and management have been accused by community members, on several occasions, of not dealing well with different situations. The question was included to analyse such perceptions.

Table 17: Respondents’ perceptions on whether Station Commanders and Branch Commanders are satisfied with training by years of service

Years of Service	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total
0 – 3	5(10.20)	19(38.78)	18(36.73)	6(12.24)	1(2.04)	49(100.00)
4 – 6	3(7.50)	19(47.50)	10(25.00)	7(17.50)	1(2.05)	40(100.00)
7 – 9	4(6.25)	33(51.56)	20(31.23)	7(10.95)	0(0.00)	64(100.00)
10 – 12	1(3.85)	12(46.15)	5(19.23)	5(19.23)	3(11.54)	26(100.00)
13	9(6.04)	67(44.97)	55(36.91)	13(8.72)	5(3.36)	149(100.00)

Total	22(6.71)	150(45.73)	108(32.93)	38(11.59)	10(3.05)	328(100.00)
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Chi-square = 17.6026 P = 0.348

In terms of categories of respondents, the ‘others’ group differed significantly from the rest of the groups at with a P-value of 0.048. Respondents who attended the CSC course also differed significantly in their responses. Table 18 shows that station commanders and branch commanders are not always satisfied with the training.

Table 18: Respondents’ perceptions on whether Station Commanders and Branch Commanders are satisfied with training by category and courses attended

Category	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Commander	2 9.09	16 10.67	9 17.43	3 8.11	0 0.00	40 12.20	5.282	1.000
Supervisor	3 13.64	23 15.33	15 13.76	6 16.22	2 20.00	49 14.94	0.416	1.000
Trainee	14 63.64	96 64.00	64 58.72	25 67.57	7 70.00	206 62.80	1.459	1.000
Trainer	3 13.64	12 8.00	9 8.26	2 5.41	1 10.00	27 8.23	1.294	1.000
Others	1 4.55	14 9.33	20 18.35	11 29.73	2 20.00	48 14.63	13.350	0.048
Total	23	161	127	47	12	370		

Courses Attended	Definitely agree	Agree	Uncertain	Disagree	Definitely disagree	Total	Chiz	PV
Detectives	2 10.00	52 35.37	29 28.71	12 34.29	4 40.00	99 31.63	6.115	1.000
Mentor	4 20.00	25 17.01	10 9.90	1 2.86	1 10.00	41 13.63	7.026	1.000
Train the trainer	1 5.00	18 12.24	10 9.90	2 5.71	0 0.00	31 9.90	3.230	1.000
Junior Management	4 20.00	19 12.93	11 10.89	4 11.43	1 10.00	39 12.46	1.389	1.000
National	2	25	13	5	0	45	3.002	1.000

Certificate	10.00	17.01	12.87	14.29	0.00	14.38		
Senior Management	1	10	6	2	0	19	0.836	1.000
CSC	5.00	6.80	5.94	5.71	0.00	6.07		
	10	33	20	10	4	77	10.153	0.303
	50.00	22.45	19.80	28.57	40.00	24.60		
Other	6	38	41	10	3	987	6.231	1.000
	30.00	25.85	40.59	28.57	30.00	31.631		
Total	30	220	140	46	13	449		

Discussions

This study's primary goal was to investigate, from the trainees' points of view, the variables influencing trainers' efficacy in providing effective instruction at the Johannesburg Training Centre. The key findings highlighted that a trainer's behaviour positively predicted training respondents' empowerment, which in turn predicted their training transfer. Findings highlighted that commanders were not provided with the feedback regarding trainees' performance. Empowering employees to feel confident and give honest, upward feedback to commanders begins by creating a culture of trust and support, one in which members are provided with an organisational support, get mentored by each other with a wide range of two-way performance feedback, that is celebratory, instructive, and constructive. The findings also highlight that the requirements for trainers' recruitment are a challenge. The researchers argue, there is documented evidence revealing that recruitment for skilful trainers has been a continuous challenge for the SAPS. The solution to both the recruitment and retention situation is systemic and lies in making teaching in the SAPS a more attractive deployment, so much so that it becomes the first choice for good graduates and its strength of recruitment is no longer subject (as it is now) a challenge. Recruitment of trainers is advantaged by the number of different routes into teaching and the extent to which this enables training, which meets the preferences and needs of individual applicants. Although substantial changes were made within the Division: HRD recently to the recruitment process, there has been little or no discussion with wider members around the effectiveness of these changes or the impact they have had on organisational level. As the shortage of skilled trainers becomes more severe, the competition for quality talent with both public and private organisation, such as institutions of higher learning, is increasing in intensity. This paper addresses results, their ramifications, and limitations in the paragraphs that follow.

Theoretical and Practical Implications

The SAPS Division's Human Resource Development (HRD) practitioners and trainers will find practical consequences from this study. There are at least two implications for HRD professionals: HRD professionals should first hire trainers who exhibit suitable trainer behaviour. The results of this study showed that branch and station commanders are not always happy with the training. Human resource development practitioners should make sure that respondents attend the training that most closely matches their profile to support meaning and competency assessments made by branch and station commanders. To do this, they may offer thorough training descriptions, work with participants to analyse their needs to select the most appropriate training, and let trainers know what to anticipate from their participants.

The findings of this study imply that through in-service and professional empowerment throughout the training, trainers can improve training transfer through transformational behaviour. According to Barling, Weber, & Kelloway (1996), transformational behaviour is a teachable skill, therefore trainers who thought they needed to get better might attend training. To demonstrate transformative conduct, trainers can do the following: for instance, by motivating participants with inspirational examples and emphasising the training's relevance to their daily tasks. Trainers could assist participants in feeling competent by considering their unique requirements and challenges. Trainers can demonstrate idealised influence and highlight the impact that participants can have by modelling behaviour. Trainers stimulate the participants' minds by asking them to consider the subjects they have addressed critically.

Limitations and Future Recommendations

There are certain restrictions with this study. The SAPS personnel from the province of Gauteng's thirteen local police stations participated in the training. Despite their diverse backgrounds, varying statuses, and positions throughout different divisions, this sample could not be entirely representative of training respondents in other South African provinces. Variations in culture could also have an impact. The readiness of training respondents for empowerment may vary based on their experiences in educational environments. Given that participants evaluated the effectiveness or conduct of trainers, it is plausible that their evaluations did not align with the trainers' real actions. As a result, authors must use caution when extrapolating findings regarding the SAPS's actual trainer efficiency. This problem might be resolved in future research with an experimental setup. Researchers could observe psychological empowerment and training transmission by manipulating the behaviour of

transformational trainers. Additionally, it would enable us to assume, something we were not able to do in this study that transformative trainer behaviour and professional empowerment are causally related.

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